

Suppl. Table 1. Antibody symbol, catalog number, company, dilution ratio, and antibody name for antibodies measured in liver tissue from periparturient dairy cows.

Antibody	Catalog Number	Company	Dilution ratio	Antibody Name
GSTM1	ARP41769_P050	Aviva Systems Biology	1:250	Glutathione S-transferase Mu 1
GSTA4	ARP48555_P050	Aviva Systems Biology	1:250	Glutathione S-transferase A4
GPX3	ARP41491_P050	Aviva Systems Biology	1:250	Glutathione peroxidase 3
MAT1A	AV41398	Sigma	1:250	Methionine adenosyltransferase I A
BHMT	AV41474	Sigma	1:250	Serine-homocysteine methyltransferase
CBS	AV45746	Sigma	1:250	Cystathionine- β -synthase
BBOX1	PA5-21477	ThermoFisher	1:200	Gamma butyrobetaine dioxygenase 1

Suppl. Figure 1. Representative western blots of target proteins analyzed in liver tissue.

